

Supplementary Information to accompany

Trinodal self-penetrating versus *cds* 3-dimensional networks using bis(3,2':6',3''-terpyridine) building blocks: the solvent makes the difference

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Supplementary figures

Figures S1–S9: NMR spectra of compounds **1a-2a** and **1b-2b**.

Figures S10–S11: Mass spectra of compounds **1b-2b**.

Figures S12–S15: Solid-state IR spectra of the compounds **1a-2a**, **1b-2b**.

Figures S16–S23: NMR spectra of the ligands **1-2**.

Figures S24–S27: Mass spectra of the ligands **1-2**.

Figures S28–S29: Solid-state IR spectra of the ligands **1-2**.

Figures S30–S33: Structural figures with atom numbering.

Figures S34–S37: Solid-state IR spectra of the coordination compounds $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{1})]_n \cdot 2n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{2})]_n \cdot 4n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$, $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 2.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$ and $[\text{Co}_2(\text{NCS})_4(\mathbf{2})_2]_n \cdot 5.5n\text{CHCl}_3 \cdot 0.2n\text{MeOH}$.

Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **1a**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S2. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **1a**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S3. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **2a**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S4. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **2a**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S5. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **1b**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O , # = CH_2Cl_2

Figure S6. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **1b**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S7. HMQC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **1b**. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3

Figure S8. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **2b**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O

Figure S9. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **2b**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S10: The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of **1b** using 2,5 dihydroxybenzoic acid as the matrix, and expansion of the base peak.

Figure S11: The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of **2b** using 2,5 dihydroxybenzoic acid as the matrix, and expansion of the base peak.

Figure S12. The solid state FT-IR spectrum of **1a**.

Figure S13. The solid state FT-IR spectrum of **2a**.

Figure S14. The solid state FT-IR spectrum of **1b**.

Figure S15. The solid state FT-IR spectrum of **2b**.

Figure S16. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **1**. * = CHCl_3

Figure S17. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **1**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S18. HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **1**. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3

Figure S19. HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **1**. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3

Figure S20. ^1H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **2**. * = CHCl_3 , § = H_2O , # = EtOH

Figure S21. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum (126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of **2**. * = CDCl_3

Figure S22. HMOC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **2**. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3

Figure S23. HMBC spectrum (^1H 500 MHz, $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ 126 MHz, CDCl_3 , 298 K) of ligand **2**. * = CHCl_3 , ** = CDCl_3

Data: CAS134-CHCA_0001.D2_(Manual) 29 September 2022 11:59:09 Cal:Custom Calibration by user1 on 29 September 2022 11:53:56 (Original)
Shimadzu MALDI-8020: Tuning Linear, Power 33, P.Ext at 360.00 (bin 49)
Processed data (averaged): 3.3 mV (sum=453.6 mV), Unsmoothed, profiles # 1 - 200

Data: CAS134-CHCA_0001.D2_(Manual) 29 September 2022 11:59:09 Cal:Custom Calibration by user1 on 29 September 2022 11:53:56 (Original)
Shimadzu MALDI-8020: Tuning Linear, Power 33, P.Ext at 360.00 (bin 49)
Processed data (averaged): 2.2 mV (sum=433.9 mV), Unsmoothed, profiles # 1 - 200

Figure S24. The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of ligand **1** with CHCA matrix, and expansion of the base peak.

Data: CAS144-CHCA_0001.D4_(Manual) 29 September 2022 12:16:03 Cal:Custom Calibration by user1 on 29 September 2022 11:53:56 (Original)
Shimadzu MALDI-8020: Tuning Linear, Power 32, P.Ext at 600.00 (bin 63)
Processed data (averaged): 3.8 mV (sum=236.5 mV), Unsmoothed, profiles # 1 - 62

Data: CAS144-CHCA_0001.D4_(Manual) 29 September 2022 12:16:03 Cal:Custom Calibration by user1 on 29 September 2022 11:53:56 (Original)
Shimadzu MALDI-8020: Tuning Linear, Power 32, P.Ext at 600.00 (bin 63)
Processed data (averaged): 1.5 mV (sum=118.4 mV), Unsmoothed, profiles # 1 - 62

Figure S25. The MALDI-TOF mass spectrum of ligand **2** with CHCA matrix, and expansion of the base peak.

Figure S26. HR-ESI mass spectrum of ligand **1** comparing the experimental isotope pattern for the base peak arising from $[M+H]^+$ (top) with the calculated isotope pattern (bottom).

Figure S27. HR-ESI mass spectrum of ligand **2** comparing the experimental isotope pattern for the base peak arising from $[M+H]^+$ (top) with the calculated isotope pattern (bottom).

Figure S28. The solid state FT-IR spectrum of ligand 1.

Figure S29. The solid state FT-IR spectrum of ligand 2.

Figure S30. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{1})]_n \cdot 2n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: i = $-x, 1-y, 1-z$; ii = $-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$; iii = $-1+x, y, -1+z$; iv = $1-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$; v = $1-x, 1-y, 2-z$; vi = $1-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$.

Figure S31. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{2})]_n \cdot 4n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; $ii = 1/2-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z$; $iii = x, y, 1+z$; $iv = 3/2-x, 1/2+y, 1/2-z$; $v = 1-x, 1-y, -z$; $vi = 3/2-x, -1/2+y, 1/2-z$.

Figure S32. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 2.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$, with symmetry generated atoms. Hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. Symmetry codes: $i = 1-x, 1-y, 1-z$; $ii = 3/2-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$; $iii = x, y, -1+z$; $iv = 1/2-x, 1/2+y, 3/2-z$; $v = 1-x, 1-y, 2-z$; $vi = 1/2-x, -1/2+y, 3/2-z$. The sulfur atom S1 of the $[\text{NCS}]^-$ unit is disordered and has been modelled over sites of 80% and 20% occupancies and only the major occupancy site is shown. The pyridine ring containing C4 is partially disordered over two orientations with 50:50% site occupancies and only one of the equal occupancies is shown. The phenylethyl substituent is disordered over four orientations with 25% occupancies each. Only one of the four equal occupancies is shown. The disordered atoms in the pyridine ring containing C4 and the phenylethyl substituent were refined isotropically.

Figure S33. The structure of the asymmetric unit in $[\text{Co}_2(\text{NCS})_4(\mathbf{2})_2]_n \cdot 5.5n\text{CHCl}_3 \cdot 0.2n\text{MeOH}$. Hydrogen atoms and solvent molecules are omitted for clarity; ellipsoids are plotted at 50% probability level. The sulfur atom S3 of the $[\text{NCS}]^-$ unit is disordered and has been modelled over sites of 55% and 45% occupancies and only the major occupancy site is shown. The cyclohexyl ring attached to O2 shows disorder over two positions with 50:50% site occupancies and only one of the equal occupancies is shown.

Figure S34. The solid state FT-IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{1})]_n \cdot 2nC_6H_4Cl_2$.

Figure S35. The solid state FT-IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}_2(\text{NCS})_4(\mathbf{2})]_n \cdot 5.5n\text{CHCl}_3 \cdot 0.2n\text{MeOH}$.

Figure S36. The solid state FT-IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{3})]_n \cdot 2.5n\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Cl}$.

Figure S37. The solid state FT-IR spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\mathbf{2})]_n \cdot 4n\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$.

